

isoQUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART VII

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The conversion of the amide (I) into the fully aromatised isoquinoline (II) under the influence of P_2O_5 in boiling xylene involves decarbonylation. The possible mechanism of the reaction has been discussed.

In Part V (this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 425) it has been recorded that ethyl α -methyl- α -acylamido- β -phenylpropionate (I: $R_2 = \text{Me}$), when subjected to the Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation with phosphorus pentoxide in boiling xylene, yields 1-alkyl- or 1-aryl-3-methylisoquinoline (II: $R_2 = \text{Me}$). Subsequent observations (Part VI, *ibid.*, 1960, 37, 111) point to the generality of this reaction, as exemplified by the different groups for R_1 and R_2 that have been studied. That this reaction involves elimination of carbon monoxide has also been recorded. In order to make a quantitative assessment of such elimination, some typical cases have now been accordingly studied. Based on the amount of amide (I) taken, it is found (Table I) that although the relative isoquinoline (II) is obtained comparatively in low yield, carbon monoxide is almost quantitatively eliminated.

TABLE I

Compound (I).		CO obtained (on theory).	Compound (II) obtained (on theory).
R_1 .	R_2 .		
Me	Me	88.33%	79.32%
Me	Et	85.33	80.00
Me	Pr	87.46	56.14
Ph	Me	91.14	62.13
CH_2Ph	Me	90.00	83.62

As ethyl formate on treatment with phosphorus pentoxide in boiling xylene is found to eliminate carbon monoxide, question may be raised whether in the conversion of (I) into (II) ethyl formate is being eliminated, which under the experimental condition is spontaneously decomposed to carbon monoxide. Such a mechanism would involve intramolecular 1:2-elimination reaction in carboxylic esters, which in literature is found to take place under pyrolytic conditions (Hurd and Blunck, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2419; Alexander and Mudrak, *ibid.*, 1950, 72, 1819, 3194; 1951, 73, 59; Barton and Rosenfelder, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2459). No evidence, however, could be obtained about such pyrolysis in the present case. For example, the amide (I: $R_1 = R_2 = \text{Me}$) or 1:3-dimethyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (Ghosh *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 758) is found to remain unchanged in boiling xylene or even in boiling diphenyl

oxide. The present reaction, however, bears some analogy to the conversion of a tertiary acid, like $\alpha\alpha$ -diphenylpropionic acid, into 1: 1-diphenylethylene with the elimination of carbon monoxide and water, when the former is heated with sulphuric acid (Bistrzycki and Reintke, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 839; cf. Welch and Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1412). Rothstein and Saville (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1961) consider that the prerequisite for the elimination of carbon monoxide in tertiary acids is the electron-releasing power of the group to which it is attached, that is the stability of the ion, $\text{CR}_2\text{-C}^+\text{O}$. It so happens that when R is alkyl, the decomposition of the ion is comparatively rapid. On this basis, the elimination of carbon monoxide from the tertiary acid derivative (I) can be understood, and a parallel mechanism can be envisaged for the present reaction, decarbonylation being initiated by electron release from the alkyl group attached to the α -carbon atom. It may be considered that phosphorus pentoxide acts as a Lewis acid and forms a complex with the ester, the (ether) oxygen of the ester transferring part of its lone pair to phosphorus, as a result of which the bond between (ether) oxygen and (carbonyl) carbon is weakened, and dissociation giving rise to a carbonium ion is possible. Reference is made to the formation of carbonium ion in the reaction of aromatic esters with aluminium chloride (Luder and Zuffanti, *Chem. Rev.*, 1944, 34, 345).

The carbonium ion then undergoes an elimination process with the elimination of a proton and carbon monoxide to afford a vinylamide, which spontaneously undergoes cyclodehydration under the experimental conditions to furnish (II). The complex with P_2O_5 may act as a proton acceptor.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general procedure followed for the estimation of carbon monoxide is recorded below :

Compound (I, 8 g.) was mixed with P_2O_5 (32 g.) and xylene (160 c.c.) in a flask fitted with an upright condenser and a CaCl_2 -guard tube. The guard tube, in its turn, was fitted to a system whereby the evolving gas could be collected in an aspirator bottle by displacement of water. The gases were forced into the aspirator under slightly reduced pressure. The system as a whole was

checked as air-tight. The flask was heated in an oil bath so that xylene refluxed smoothly and the operation was continued for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and treated with crushed ice. The base was isolated according to the procedure described in Parts V and VI (*loc. cit.*).

The gases collected in the aspirator were analysed in a standard Orsat apparatus. Carbon dioxide was absorbed in 33% solution of KOH. The trapped oxygen of the system was then absorbed in potassium pyrogallate solution (10 g. of pyrogallol in 200 c.c. of 50% aqueous KOH solution). Carbon monoxide was absorbed in ammoniacal cuprous chloride solution (23 g. cuprous chloride, 86 c.c. liquor ammonia and 100 c.c. water).

The pressure and temperature of the collected gases were determined accurately and the amount of carbon monoxide obtained was calculated at N. T. P. after taking into consideration the aqueous tension.

The authors are indebted to Dr. U. P. Basu, Director of the Institute, for his kind interest in this investigation. They are also thankful to the Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, Government of India, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship (to B. K. G.) and a maintenance grant.

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Received April 18, 1961.